

A COMMUNICATIVE PRAGMATIC STUDY OF MEANS OF EXPRESSING DIRECTIVE SPEECH ACTS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Communication is a product of human thinking, and in this process, speakers create various speech structures (speech acts) aimed at different goals. A speech act is a speech act directed at a specific goal, accepted by members of society and performed in accordance with the rules of speech behavior.

The emergence and study of the speech act problem in linguistics is connected with the philosophical views of the Australian philosopher L. Wittgenstein on the issue of linguistic activity. The theory of the speech act was first put forward by the English philosopher J. Austin. In the book "How to do things with words" published after his death, the theory of speech act and the classification of speech acts were dissolved. Speech act has a strong relation in linguistics. Speech act itself has a performative function which emphasizes

ABSTRACT

Communicative pragmatic studies are taking many linguists' attention which is very important in linguistics. Some researches have been done in this field, however there are still too many questions that need answers. In this article, we are going to analyze directive speech acts in English and Uzbek languages.

an action between the interlocutors. The performative function is very important in communication so that the speech act will talk about the function of language in communication and also an action expressed by the interlocutors. In understanding the speech act, a situation behind an action must be considered.

Austin in his theory of language and action distinguishes three kinds of acts; they are the locutionary, the illocutionary, and the perlocutionary. Then explanation each kind of acts as follows according to Sadock.

a. Locutionary act is performed to communicate.

b. Illocutionary act is speech accomplished by communicating the intentions to accomplish them.

c. The perlocutionary act is the by-products of acts communication. It is the act

performed by the hearer as an effect on the speaker's utterance.

Searle defines directives are that kind of speech act that represent attempts by the speaker to get the addressee to do something. This definition is also supported by Yule. Considering the above description, it can be seen that the most prominent context in directive speech act is about the hearer and the relationship between speaker and hearer in both English and Uzbek language. Relationship between speaker and hearer can be an indicator that makes the speaker use a different way to ask a question, make a request, or issue an invitation.

Based on its functions of English and Uzbek language, Directive speech acts can be used as Command, Request, Prohibition, and Question. The description is as follows:

Command

Commands are sentences which normally have no overt grammatically subject, and whose verb is in the imperative mood. The command is also used to instruct somebody to do something. It tends to be demanding, means that the order must be fulfilled.

Example: Just get out of here!

Get a computer and track my phone!

No. Stop!

Request

A request is a way of ordering something from the hearer. The request is not like a command, it is generally less demanding. The example is could you "lend me a pen, please?". In some cases, a request tends to use hints to produce a request. Searle in Cole (1975) states that sometimes a speaker may utter the sentence "I want you to do it" by way of requesting the hearer to do something. Here, the utterance is incidentally meant as a statement, but

actually, it is also meant primarily as a request made by way of making a statement.

Example: Do you want to go with me?

Let's just go home.

Come on Ned, please.

Prohibition

Prohibition means to prevent the hearer from doing something. For example: "Don't touch that!"

No, Stay!

I said not now!

Question

Searle classifies question as a kind of directives speech act since they attempt a speaker to get the hearer to answer that question. It means that a question is also performing a speech act. Questioning performatives include: ask, inquire, query, question and quiz.

Example:

What's your name?

What year are you?

Do you know who I am?

By studying the English and Uzbek languages based on pragmatics, we can get bid advantages. We can talk about people's intended meanings, their assumptions, their goals, and the kinds of action (request, refusal, agreement, thanking, apologizing, etc) when they are speaking. And to achieve success in communication, a speaker from one language should understand the meaning and effects of utterances in relation to the context and the speaker's intention.

In the context of learning Uzbek linguistics, people may understand about sociolinguistics, politeness strategies, speech act, or maxims of conversation. Those categories of linguistics studies can be used to learn a language particularly in communicating with others. One of the

linguistics studies which have a close relationship in communication is speech act. According to Searle, speech act refers to linguistic communications which present intention behavior. Speech acts are the way of people how to understand a speaker's intention through some utterances delivered by them.

Directive speech acts is a kind of speech act that the speaker uses to get someone else to do something. The speaker tries to get the listener to do an act such as a way to do a future action according to the intention of the speaker.

References:

1. Abrams, M.H. A Glossary of Literary Terms. Penyunt. United state of Amerika. New York: Harcourt College, 1999.
2. Cutting, Joan. Pragmatics and Discourse : A Reource Book for students. London: Routledge, 2002.
3. Hymes, Dell. Foundation of Sociolinguistics. London and New York: Longman, 1974.
4. Azimjon Latifjon oqli Melikuziev. (2022). HISTORICAL AND MODERN CLASSIFICATION OF PARALINGUISTICS. *Academica Globe: Inderscience Research*, 3(10), 126–128. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/UAH57>
5. 10. Khakimov, M. K., & ugli Melikuziev, A. L. (2022). The History of Paralinguistic Researches. *International Journal of Culture and Modernity*, 13, 90-95. Jorgensen, M and Philips. *Discourse Analysis as Theory and Method*. London, 2002.
6. Kreidler, C.W. *Introducing English Semantics*. New York and London: Routledge, 1998.
7. Levinson, S.C. A. *Pragmatics*. Cambridge: Press Syndicate of the University of Cambridge, 1983.
8. McCarthy, M J. "Discussing Discourse. Birmingham English Language Research." *Interactive Lexis: Prominence and Paradigms* (1987).
9. Michaels, S. "Text and Context: A New Approach to the Study of Classroom Writing." *Discourse Processes* (1987): 321-83.
10. Ubaydullaeva, D., & Yuldasheva, Z. (2020). POLYSEMY IN THE UZBEK LANGUAGE. In *АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ СОВРЕМЕННОЙ НАУКИ И ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ* (pp. 234-235).
11. Ubaydullayeva, D., & Raxmonqulova, M. (2022). DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIAL DIRECTION IN LINGUISTICS. *Science and Innovation*, 1(6), 869-873.